

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARMENIAN SOURCES IN THE STUDIES OF THE TIMURID HISTORY

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The Armenian history writing experienced its most productive period in the Chinggisid era. Specifically the Armenians that were subject to the Ilkhanates in the Near East, making use of the freedom provided by this protection, made their appearance on the stage of history, both as the closest witnesses of the events, and the volunteering participants of the Ilkhanate activities as well. In this regard, the Medieval Armenian chroniclers carry quite detailed information about the Chinggisids.

Yet, the 15th century, or the Timurid era poses as an exception to the preceding era in this regard. The number of the individual history records written in this century saw a good deal of decrease, compared to the previous eras. The reason for that, probably, might be that the Timurids didn't show religious tolerance to their Christian subjects that the Ilkhanates did until they assumed Islam. Since the Near Eastern Christian folks were not happy with living under the hegemony of the Muslim Arabs and Turks for the preceding centuries, they regarded the Chinggisids as a kind of saviors. In this regard, the era of Timur and successors, offers some difference from the Chinggisid Empire. It might be thought, naturally, that this deal was affective in the Armenian history writing to enter into a period of stagnation.

Again, thank to the Armenian colophons that were written in the 15th century, it is possible to find information about the acts of Timur and his successors. These Armenian colophons provide quite limited information, compared to the individual history books. Therefore the Armenian colophons has a feature that we may normally classify as abstracts. In addition to that, they were usually penned by the Armenian clergy, shrouded in a religious bigotry. A good deal of anti-Islamic style and supernatural depictions show their influence in these works. On the other hand, they show a regional essence. So, they act from the centre of the incidents and do not provide much detail beyond a city or a monastery. Because of this, the majority of the information in the Armenian colophons were dedicated to the Caucasian expedition, defined as the "triennial" expedition. The acts of Timur in Armenia and Georgia were reflected from a strong Christian point of view.

The Armenian colophons, on the other hand, mentioned Timur's relations with the Aq Qoyunlu and Qara Qoyunlu Turkmans. They carry quite valuable information, especially in terms of the struggles of Qara Yusuf and his son Iskandar against Timur. Moreover, the Armenian colophons occupy an extremely important position in the Timurid history studies, for that they also touch the 1420 Battle of Ankara, which took place between the Ottoman Bayezid the Thunderbolt and Timur. At least, the information as reflected in the Armenian colophons are coherent with the information as transmitted by the Timurid historians such as Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi and Nizam al-Din Shami. The 14th century Armenian colophons that provide information about the Timurid era were published by L.S. Hachikyan among the publications of the Armenian Soviet Academy of Sciences [1]. The colophons from the 15th century were published, again, by Hachikyan, in a separate volume [2]. Another publication on the Armenian colophons about the Timurids is by B. Sargisyan. Gathering the Armenian manuscripts in Venice, Sargisyan published in 1919 [3]. Those who lack of Armenian knowledge may use the texts, partially translated by Sanjian in English [4].

The work which provides the largest information about Timur and his successors is by Tovma Metzobetsi [5]. The 15th century author is the abbot of Tovma monastery. The work he entitled as "History of Tamarlane and Successors" mentions, specifically, the acts of Timur and Mirza Shahruh in the Western Asia. Tovma was captured by Timur couple of times, closely witnessed the Muslim bigotry, and he penned incidents he witnessed in a sensitiveness of a religious man. The work was penned in the tone of an elegy in general. It contains the subjects such as Timur's appearance on the stage of history, his march to Caucasus, his relation with the Golden Horde ruler Tokhtamysh, the wars waged with the Aq Qoyunlu and the Qara Qoyunlu, and the enslavement of the Ottoman Bayezid the Thunderbolt by Timur. The work also deserves a good deal of place to the state organization of Timur, and the terminology used in that era. In this regard, the work bears on the linguists, as much as it does on the historians. Yet, as the author states himself, since the incidents were written down 50 years after, the information given by Tovma should be handled with a reserve.

And about the publication of Tovma's work, the work claimed the attention of the scholars early, and was published in Armenian, for the first time in 1860 in Paris by Karapet Shahnazaryan, a member of the Armenian church. In the preface that Shahnazaryan wrote in Armenian, about the Tovma's work, says:

"Tovma, who was the abbot of Metzob monastery in the Greater Armenia, lived in the 15th century, and penned a series of useful works, containing the story of the expedition and destruction by the bloodthirsty beast Tamarlane, in Armenia and

surrounding lands; the author who fell into the hands of savage Tartars more than once, and who himself frequently experienced the horror of slavery, persecution, and Muslim bigotry, surveyed the history of the misfortunes of the Christian Armenians by tears rather than ink. Tovma is the seventh author of our Armenian History Series, that went to press.

When we published the book, we only had a manuscript, moreover this manuscript was very correct and complete; another manuscript with the similar quality was in the Imperial Lybrary in Paris; in order to elucidate som ambiguities and to point the differences between the two works in the notes, we used it to compare our manuscript.

Under such conditions, in order the universal general history of the whole Asia to be known, we offer the seventh volume of the very fruitful and useful Armenian history series to the scientific world.” [5, B.2].

Other than Shahnazaryan, Félix Nève abbreviated this work, added comments, and published in 1860, in Brusselss, in French. In 1957, it was translated into the Azerbaijan language through the Russian translation by J. Bakikhanov, and was published in Baku as an abstract. Robert Bedrosian translated the work in English in 1987. And in Turkey, the full text of this work was translated by İlhan Aslan in 2024.

As a result, we see the Armenian sources occupy a prominent place in the Timurid history. Yet, these sources that provide rich data about the Timurs still wait to be studied by the first hands. As such information was processed and brought to daylight, it appears to us as a reality that the missing parts about the Timurid era would be completed.

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